

Training Protocol and Deployments

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D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

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D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

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Equal-Life: Training Protocol and Deployments Table of contents

Equal-Life: Training Protocol and Deployments Table of contents	4
1. Training Strategy and Stakeholder-Oriented Implementation	6
1.1 Training Framework and Stakeholder Engagement	6
1.2 Stakeholder Needs and Input.....	6
1.3 Training Goals	7
2. Target audience	7
2.1 Collaboration with (local) partners and European networks	8
3. Process of training development.....	9
3.1 Training preparation	9
3.2 Number & type of trainings	12
3.3 Timeline	12
4. Scope of the training	13
4.1 Translated into Training Sessions.....	14
4.1.1 Session 1: Setting the Stage – Understanding the Exposome and the Equal-Life Project	14
4.1.2 Session 2: Exploring the Exposome in Practice – Recognising Elements in Real-World Contexts	14
4.1.3 Session 3: Applying the Toolbox – Hands-On Use in Policy or Intervention Contexts	15
5. Trainings – final format & execution	16
5.1 Pilots	16
5.1.1 Primary Audience.....	16
5.1.2 Pilots: Purpose and Format.....	17
5.1.3 Intervention/Policy Case Application.....	17
5.1.4 Target Audience per Pilot	17
5.2 Online training sessions	18
5.2.1 Target Audience.....	18
5.2.2 Training Objectives	18
5.2.3 Language and Format	18
5.3 In-person training sessions	19

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- 5.3.1 Ljubljana 11 November 2024 19
- 5.3.2 In-Person Training & Conference Contribution – Vienna (EUROCITIES Environment Forum 2024) 22
- 5.3.3 Amsterdam, linked to End-event Equal-Life – 7 April 2025..... 23
- 5.3.4 Barcelona -“Eurocities Academy” – 5-6 May 2025..... 24
- 5.3.5 Cairo -“Eurocities Academy” – 5-6 May 26
- 5.3.6 Stockholm – Local training 10 June 2025 27
- 5.3.7 Izmir – Healthy Cities 20 June 2025 29
- 6. Annexes..... 31
 - 6.1 Annex 1: Pilot Training Agenda – Amsterdam template 31
 - 6.2 Annex 2: Online training Agenda template 32
 - 6.3 Annex 3: Slido general format..... 33
 - 6.4 Annex 4 – In person Ljubljana Training Agenda 34
 - 6.5 Annex 5: Eurocities detailed agenda and roadmap..... 36
 - 6.5.1 Roadmap..... 36
 - 6.5.2 Agenda..... 39
 - 6.6 Annex 6: In person training Izmir 2025 detailed program..... 43

1. Training Strategy and Stakeholder-Oriented Implementation

1.1 Training Framework and Stakeholder Engagement

The training sessions are a part of the Equal-Life project and were set up taking into account several main objectives:

- To familiarize stakeholders with Equal-Life as a project, as well as generating understanding of its concepts;
- To introduce the Equal-Life Toolbox and provide a comprehensive understanding of its components;
- To guide stakeholders on how to apply the toolbox within their specific professional or policy contexts.

In parallel, the trainings sought to create a broader awareness of the range of factors that influence mental health and cognitive development in children and adolescents, highlighting the interconnected nature of these factors within the exposome framework. Also see 1.3 on Training goals.

A key consideration throughout the training activities was to ensure that the focus would not be limited to the exposome alone. The central theme was the assumed association between the exposome and mental health and cognitive development in children. The training modules were designed to support Equal-Life stakeholders in adopting and utilising the Equal-Life Toolbox in order to improve children's living environments through integrated, evidence-based approaches.

1.2 Stakeholder Needs and Input

During the stakeholder meetings organized in the framework of Equal-Life as well as during the pilot training sessions, stakeholders were consulted on their needs and requirements to adopt the Equal-Life project tools results. Our key recurring themes and related questions shaped the focus of the training content:

- **Understanding of Concepts:** What is the exposome? How mental health and cognitive development defined in the context of Equal-Life?
- **Contextual Relevance:** How can local issues and challenges be addressed from an Equal-Life and exposome perspective? Stakeholders emphasised the importance of tailoring the training to their specific contexts.
- **Tool Selection and Application:** Which tools are appropriate for designing targeted interventions that reflect the complex interplay between the exposome and mental

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

health? Stakeholders expressed interest in practical recommendations and guidance on applying Equal-Life tools in routine policy development and implementation.

Together with the stakeholders who were part of these early meetings (throughout 2022-2024), several specific learning needs were identified. They requested clear guidance on the types of content and contexts that are most relevant for their work, especially regarding vulnerable groups, pressing health issues, and potential interventions. Rather than lengthy technical documents or complex interfaces, stakeholders preferred concise narratives and summary formats (e.g. two-page briefs) highlighting key messages and practical applications.

When it comes to tool adoption, stakeholders expressed a preference for accessible, user-friendly instruments that require minimal input. Their main concern was how to make informed decisions about public investments. As such, they are looking for reliable information to support prioritisation, rather than tools requiring complex data entry or modelling.

1.3 Training Goals

Based on the task description in the Grant Agreement, and aligned with stakeholder input, the training was designed to fulfil three key ambitions:

- **Knowledge Transfer:** Provide stakeholders with foundational knowledge about the exposome, the Equal-Life project, and the components of the toolbox.
- **Interdisciplinary discussions:** gaining experience with application of the Equal-Life approach, concepts, insights by looking at (existing) exposome cases in local contexts, essential in the exposome approach;
- **Toolbox dissemination & Contextual Tool Application:** Introduce the stakeholders with the toolbox & guidebook and equip stakeholders with the knowledge needed to identify and apply the most appropriate tools for their context. This included explaining the rationale behind the development of each tool, supported by relevant case studies within the project.

With the overall aim of disseminating the Equal-Life project's work and the dissemination and future adoption of the toolbox in practice, each training format developed had its own specific objectives and level of depth, tailored to various stakeholder groups. These are described in detail in the respective training format documentation.

2. Target audience

The training activities were designed for a broad and diverse group of stakeholders, spanning multiple disciplines and sectors. Recognising the complex and interdisciplinary nature of exposome research, mental health and cognitive development, the trainings aimed to address the people in practice and policy working in related fields and related policy themes.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

By bringing together individuals with expertise in these distinct domains, the training fosters mutual understanding and the integration of diverse perspectives into their respective professional practices. A particular emphasis is placed on engaging local and regional actors. These include representatives of municipalities, regional public health institutes, urban planners, people in education, epidemiologists, clinical practitioners, and social project managers. These individuals are often embedded within local-regional networks and are well-positioned to apply the Equal-Life toolbox in practical settings, thereby enhancing the relevance and impact of the training outcomes.

Furthermore, we aimed to tap into European networks to reach out to policymakers from various countries and cities who could disseminate the Equal-Life work further.

To ensure relevance and effectiveness, the training content is tailored to the specific needs and interests of each target group. This is facilitated through preliminary discussions with institutes or representatives (see also section 2.1). Based on these pre-training exchanges, emphasis could be placed on selected topics that align with the participants' roles, expertise, and contextual priorities.

Three distinct training formats have been developed to accommodate varying stakeholder needs and logistical contexts: pilot sessions, online modules, and in-person workshops.

The list of stakeholders, which was also used during the interview phase, serves as the foundation for outreach and engagement in the training activities. However, for effective dissemination and broader uptake of the Equal-Life toolbox, it remained essential to extend this network and involve a wider audience beyond the initial stakeholder group.

2.1 Collaboration with (local) partners and European networks

Within Equal-Life's large consortium, many partners who are connected to, or working closely together with, local and regional institutes that represent a group of stakeholders or are in the network of stakeholders. Furthermore, some partners are involved in high level European networks, focused on (for example) policy making in European cities. After defining who the Equal-Life stakeholders are (see section above), the training team identified partners that could help in organizing trainings in their local contexts. Furthermore, our partner from the City of Utrecht was able to connect the Equal-Life training to European city networks, such as 'Eurocities' (with over 200 cities participating) and the World Health Organization's 'Healthy cities' network.

By collaborating with Equal-Life partners and their local networks, we aim to target stakeholders efficiently and in a way that is suitable to their local context and culture. They have been key in organizing these meetings in a way that works for the participants. Additionally, working with Equal-Life's partners that are familiar with these institutes or networks adds to the credibility and the project and its results, as there is already a connection there.

Through this collaboration, we were able to work with partners and connections from, and host in the context of, Germany, Italy, Sweden, Slovenia, Barcelona (Spain), Ireland, Egypt, the Netherlands and Turkey. As such, we have been successful in conveying the insights and information on the Equal-Life project in a wide European context and beyond.

3. Process of training development

3.1 Training preparation

The training team started its organization of the trainings at the end of 2023. In the run up of the trainings, the roles and responsibilities within the months to come were defined and agreed upon as follows:

- **RIVM (Task lead)** – oversees & coordinates training trajectory, organizes & chairs meetings, translates, keeps track of progress in a collaborative training document;
- **RIVM (Coordinator)** monitors expectations (proposal- what did we promise) & execution from project point of view;
- **Quantia (Tools, Training and Implementation work package lead)** – Delivers tools, organizer (logistically and physically, financially, as well as content (together with people from consortium) and programme;
- **INCHES & CoU (communication lead and co-lead)**– in charge of stakeholders outreach and input: including advising on format and content of trainings that match wishes of stakeholders, reaching out (dissemination) to stakeholders for participation, responsible for harboring participation of stakeholders;
- **Others with hours for training in Tools, training and implementation (incl experts)** – actively help organizing contributing and teaching (at specific locations).

Overall, partners as listed above were expected to participate in the training (organising and executing), based on their availability.

Step wise, the definition of the training target audience, aims and objectives, scope and timeline were defined first. These are reflected in various sections in this document.

Subsequently, the training formats were developed in a way that was feasible in terms of timing and finances, yet would match the task description, identified aims of the task and the needs of the stakeholders.

Thirdly, the organization efforts for the individual trainings started. First, the organizing team was determined. The core training team was kept up to date on the training plans and were allocated to add to the organizational efforts of the trainings based on their availability.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

Within this step, the (local) partners to help organize the training was taken on into the training development team.

Next came the programme (content) planning and logistics. Due to the ongoing work and incoming results of the project, this required an iterative process. This required a lot of work and alignment with the project partners and PIs. Meetings were pre-planned to ensure enough contact points before the training execution to prepare accordingly.

More than 50 meetings have been held to prepare for the individual trainings.

For outreach, we relied on the collaboration with (local) partners and European networks. The training team combined efforts in this. A separate email address was installed for registration and questions on trainings. Furthermore, the website was used as a primary source with information and links to register for trainings. A flyer was developed to be disseminated at events in physical form (such as EHEN meetings and Euro cities conference in Vienna), as well as an attachment in an online format. This flyer presented information on Equal-Life as a project itself, as well as an invitation to online trainings (see picture below).

Studying the exposome

for a healthier future for all children

From conception, children are exposed to a range of environmental factors during their development. How does the totality of these exposures – or ‘the exposome’ – in early life affect children’s mental health & cognitive development later on?

Equal-Life addresses this relationship by linking data from over 250 thousand European children on physical, social and internal exposures to mental health and cognitive data. Understanding how early life exposures impact children’s mental health & cognitive development later in life is crucial to develop healthier (urban) environments that can support their well-being.

The Equal-Life project...

Innovates

- Combines exposure data from birth cohorts, school studies & new sources
- Tests impact of multiple exposures using new statistical methods
- Investigates physical & social exposure aspects together
- Co-designs with stakeholders

Defines

- Early markers for mental health & cognitive development
- Sleep, coping and stress/restoration as key mechanisms
- (environmental) Health promoting and risk factors for mental health & cognitive development

Explores

- Interventions & policies for preventive action at life stages: prenatal - 21 yrs. old
- Quality of places relevant for children

Creates

For people in practice:

- Online toolbox & guidance
- In-person & online trainings

Learn more at www.equal-life.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 874724

European Human **Exposome NETWORK**

3.2 Number & type of trainings

A structured training programme was developed and implemented throughout the project. The overall objective was to deliver between 12 and 15 training sessions in multiple formats targeting the identified group of Equal-Life stakeholders.

To accommodate for different levels of familiarity with the exposome concept, as well as varying stakeholder needs and contexts, multiple training formats were employed. including pilot trainings, online introductory sessions, in-person workshops, and shorter presentations at external events such as conferences and congresses.

The table below summarises the number and types of trainings carried out or planned, indicating their duration, intended audience, and the project teams responsible for their coordination and delivery.

Training	Number	Length	Target audience
Pilots (In-person)	2	1 day	1 local institute
Online (introduction) training	7	2-2.5 hrs	Broad, EVERY stakeholder
In-person trainings (advanced exposome session, guiding stakeholders, hands on toolbox training)	6	½ - 1 ½ day	Targeted local stakeholders (based on location) & those interested from online meetings Networks
Shorter training introductions during congress or international meetings	3	NA	Congress participants

3.3 Timeline

The development and delivery of the Equal-Life training activities followed a phased implementation timeline spanning from late 2023 to mid-2025. The timeline reflects the refinement of training concepts, the development of materials, and the execution of training formats across different countries and stakeholder groups.

Initial activities in 2023 focused on finalising the training concept and preparing materials for the first pilot sessions. These pilots, conducted in early 2024, informed the subsequent development of an online training module and multilingual adaptations. From late 2024 through 2025, the training activities were scaled up and diversified to include online sessions, in-person workshops, and contributions to international events and congresses.

The table below outlines the key milestones and training activities across quarters, detailing the dates, formats, and geographic focus of each session.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

Year	Q	Date	Activity
2023	Q4		Formulating and completing training concepts and formats
2024	Q1		Develop first online introduction trainings Develop material for the first pilots
	Q2		Pilots (in-person) 1. Cork (21 May) 2. Amsterdam (25 June)
	Q3		July-August: development phase online training module & translations Sept: translations & start outreach / communication
	Q4	Mon 11 November Tue 12 November	In-person – Ljubljana, Slovenia – full in person training In-person - Vienna EUROCITIES (Dissemination Equal-Life & introduction Working Group Noise) 12 November – congress contribution (intro)
2025	Q1	Tues 28 January Wed 5 February Wed 12 February Thurs 20 March	Italian online training (26 participants) Dutch online training (24 participants) German online training (13 participants) Kickoff meeting Eurocities Academy (online)
	Q2	Mon. 7 April Thurs 24 April Mon-Tues 5-6 May Sun 11 May Tues 10 June Fri 20 June	In-person training connected to End Event Equal-Life – Amsterdam, Netherlands English online training (related to Eurocities Academy - 34 participants) In-person training – Eurocities Academy, Barcelona, Spain (EU-wide participation) In-person training – Cairo, Egypt (Green Economy Academy – Climate Change, Migration and Health (GEA-CCMH)) In-person workshop – Stockholm, Sweden – Karolinska Institute In-person training – Healthy Cities Conference- Izmir, Turkey
	Q3	Mon 7 July TBD Wed 23 July	Online training – Municipal Health Service – national level NL Online training – Municipal Health Service - Cork IRL Online training – National Medical Associations: ISDE – national level Italy

4. Scope of the training

The training programme was designed to inform, demonstrate, and actively engage stakeholders in understanding and applying the Equal-Life exposome approach, insights and toolbox (see also section 1.3). The scope of the training reflects a progression in depth and interactivity, starting from basic conceptual understanding, moving through guided demonstrations, and culminating in hands-on application to real-world contexts. The aim was to provide stakeholders not only with knowledge about the exposome and its relevance to mental health and cognitive development in children, but also with practical tools and frameworks they could apply in their own institutional settings. By doing so, the training encourages stakeholders to consider how elements of the Equal-Life approach could translate into their own practice, policy design, or research.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

The training was structured into a series of sessions, each with a specific focus and learning objective. These sessions can be delivered individually or combined, depending on the needs of the audience.

4.1 Translated into Training Sessions

4.1.1 Session 1: Setting the Stage – Understanding the Exposome and the Equal-Life Project

The first session provides the conceptual foundation for the training. It introduces participants to the Equal-Life project and to the core idea of the exposome, particularly in relation to mental health and cognitive development in children and adolescents. The objective is to inform and equip stakeholders with a solid understanding of the underlying concepts, definitions, and the scientific rationale of the project.

Participants are introduced to:

- The Equal-Life project and consortium
- The EHEN network
- The Equal-Life conceptual framework
- Relevant definitions and terminology
- Key exposures identified in cohorts and in-depth studies
- Mediators and outcomes, framed within a stakeholder-relevant context
- Settings and age groups covered by the project
- Identified data gaps and potential future enrichment strategies
- Methodology used to perform the Equal-Life research

Besides providing basic understanding of the project necessary to progress to the following sessions in the training, this session aims to help stakeholders grasp how and why the exposome approach is relevant to their context, what aspects of Equal-Life may be transferable to their practice or policy domain, and how to identify the right stakeholders and departments within their organisation to engage further.

Supporting materials are provided to facilitate dissemination and internal discussion, including visual and textual summaries of the project and its concepts.

4.1.2 Session 2: Exploring the Exposome in Practice – Recognising Elements in Real-World Contexts

Building on the conceptual foundation laid in Session 1, this session invites participants to engage in practical reflection and discussion, using concrete examples to explore how exposome-related factors manifest in everyday environments.

The goal is not yet to apply the Equal-Life toolbox, but to recognise and discuss exposome dimensions using:

- Photographs or visual scenarios provided by the trainers, illustrating real or simulated settings with various environmental and social exposures (used in online settings);

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Real-life cases such as sites visited in the local context, hosted by the local partners;
- Real-life cases brought by the participants themselves, drawn from their professional contexts.

These materials are used to prompt discussion, in in-person settings: group work, and reflection on:

- How to describe/interpret the exposome in this situation
- Which types of exposures are present or relevant in this given context
- How these might relate to mental health and cognitive development
- How such insights could be used to inform (new) policy

This session fosters critical thinking, collaborative interpretation, and peer learning. It also helps stakeholders internalise the exposome perspective and prepares them for later application of the toolbox in their own cases.

4.1.3 Session 3: Applying the Toolbox – Hands-On Use in Policy or Intervention Contexts

The third session is designed as a hands-on workshop focused on the practical use of the Equal-Life toolbox and handbook. Participants are encouraged to apply the tools to cases they are familiar with from their own organisations, policy work, or community-level initiatives.

The session includes:

- Live, guided exploration of the toolbox and handbook
- Application of the tools to stakeholder-identified policy cases
- Group discussions on what participants discover, potential challenges, and opportunities for integrating the toolbox into existing workflows
- Reflection on how the tools could be shared with colleagues or scaled within their institutions
- Optional component: on how to train others in the use of the toolbox

This session is aimed at familiarizing with the Equal-Life toolbox, promoting its use and building confidence and competence in the practical application of the toolbox; overall stimulating stakeholders to share the knowledge and practical output in the shape of the toolbox within their own networks.

5. Trainings – final format & execution

This section provides a detailed account of the training activities implemented during the final phase of the Equal-Life project.

The training goals, scope and preparation – as explained in chapters 1-4 in this manuscript – led to a variety of training formats ranging from in-person pilot sessions and online modules to contributions at international conferences. The trainings took place across multiple European cities and online platforms, ensuring broad geographical reach and accessibility, and were all tailored to diverse stakeholder needs and regional contexts.

Each training opportunity served a specific function: pilot sessions in Cork and Amsterdam tested and refined initial materials; the summer development phase focused on translating content and preparing outreach strategies; and a series of sessions between late 2024 and mid-2025 further expanded implementation, including thematic deep-dives, collaborative workshops, and strategic dissemination events (e.g. through EUROCITIES and the Eurocities Academy). The following subsections describe each of these trainings in more detail, including their objectives, structure, target audience, and outcomes.

5.1 Pilots

The pilot trainings served as a first opportunity to test and refine the Equal-Life training approach in a real-world setting. Conducted as full-day sessions, these pilots aimed to validate the structure, content, and facilitation methods of the proposed training format. Each session was followed by a co-design workshop with selected stakeholders from our network to gather direct feedback and collaboratively shape the further development of the training.

Rather than focusing on individual tools in isolation, the pilots introduced the Equal-Life Toolbox as a structured way of thinking—offering insights into how to approach complex cases through the lens of the exposome. As observed during the sessions, the value of the toolbox lies not only in its components, but in how it supports stakeholders in framing, analysing, and acting upon interrelated environmental and social factors that influence children's mental health and cognitive development. The pilots helped establish a foundation for the subsequent training sessions by highlighting what resonated with participants, identifying areas for improvement, and ensuring that the materials were both accessible and practically useful in diverse local contexts.

5.1.1 Primary Audience

The primary audience for the pilot sessions included local professionals and policy-makers who contribute to the design and implementation of interventions and policies related to children's mental health and cognitive development. Target stakeholder groups included:

- Educators and healthcare professionals who directly support children and young people
- Community leaders representing local perspectives and needs

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Experts in policy planning and evaluation
- Urban planners and environmental scientists working on healthy living environments
- Researchers and practitioners in sociology and equity-related fields
- Other professionals engaged in cross-sectoral child wellbeing initiatives

Given that participants come from various professional backgrounds, the training also aims to facilitate transdisciplinary dialogue, helping stakeholders integrate different perspectives in their daily work and decisions.

5.1.2 Pilots: Purpose and Format

To refine the training design and improve content delivery, two pilot sessions were organised—in Amsterdam, Netherlands and Cork, Ireland. These sessions were intended to test the programme structure (divided into the three sessions as described in section 4), pedagogical approach, and toolbox application, while simultaneously gathering feedback from participants to guide further improvements.

The pilots allowed participants to familiarise themselves with the project and toolbox while exploring how these tools could be used to evaluate or enhance existing local policies or interventions related to children’s health. In this co-creative setting, stakeholders also contributed to the refinement of materials, formats, and messaging.

5.1.3 Intervention/Policy Case Application

As part of the training, participants were invited to reflect on either a provided case study or an example drawn from their own professional context. The aim was to apply the Equal-Life framework to assess interventions or policies from an exposome-informed perspective, based on the available project results.

- A guided, live application of the toolbox was conducted, with questions such as:
- How do the insights from Equal-Life affect your view of this intervention or policy?
- Are all relevant stakeholders and sectors represented?
- What environmental or social factors are being addressed or overlooked?

This exercise was intended to show how the toolbox can support structured reflection and lead to more integrated, comprehensive approaches in the development and evaluation of local health-related interventions.

In preparation for each pilot, local organisers were asked to select a suitable example to be explored during the training, ensuring the case would resonate with the audience’s context.

5.1.4 Target Audience per Pilot

Cork: A diverse group of local policy-makers and practitioners, Cork municipality network. (Number of participants 20 representatives from Cork municipality, city associations and international stakeholders)

Amsterdam: Professionals from the Public Health Service of Amsterdam (GGD) and potentially broader stakeholder groups beyond municipal departments, supported by Fred Woudenberg.

(Number of participants: 15 representatives from Amsterdam municipality and city associations)

See detailed program in [Annex 1: Pilot Training Agenda – Amsterdam template](#)

5.2 Online training sessions

The online training sessions were delivered in the form of interactive webinars, designed to introduce stakeholders to the Equal-Life project, its key results, and the Equal-Life Toolbox. These sessions also provided participants with the opportunity to reflect on how the newly acquired knowledge could be applied within their own professional contexts.

The primary objectives of the online training were to introduce and familiarize participants with the exposome approach and the Equal-Life Toolbox, and to enthuse stakeholders for future use of the tools and project outcomes.

5.2.1 Target Audience

The target audience was broad and included all stakeholder groups identified and described in section 2 as potentially interested in the application of exposome-informed approaches in policy and practice.

5.2.2 Training Objectives

The online sessions were structured around the following goals (in line with the sessions as described in section 4 of this document):

- Inform participants about the Equal-Life project and introduce the exposome concept, including a general overview of findings on how the exposome relates to children’s mental health and cognitive development (Session 1);
- Encourage reflection and adoption of the information from session 1, prompting participants to consider various cases through visual representations of real-life situations from an exposome-informed perspective (Session 2);
- Introduce and demonstrate the Equal-Life Toolbox, guiding participants through its purpose, structure, and potential applications (Session 3).

Enable follow-up, offering participants the opportunity to stay in touch with the training organizers.

5.2.3 Language and Format

To maximise inclusiveness and relevance across different national contexts, the webinars were delivered in a standardised format, with moderation offered in multiple languages.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

While all presentations were provided in English to reduce preparation time and ensure consistency across sessions, discussions, facilitation, and participant interaction were conducted in the local language of the audience. This approach ensured optimal understanding while respecting capacity limitations during a period of high training activity.

Detailed Agenda in [Annex 2: Online training Agenda template](#)

Detailed timetable in Section [Training preparation](#) on main document

5.3 In-person training sessions

The in-person training sessions provided an opportunity for stakeholders to engage more directly and interactively with Equal-Life consortium members as representatives of the project on the project's work and outcomes, as well as the Equal-Life Toolbox. These trainings included more focused sessions defined based on the availability of project partners, the local context and the timing and progress of the project. In some of the in-person training cases, this resulted in more focused sessions for session 2: Exploring the Exposome in Practice.

Rather than exploring the full toolbox in detail, the emphasis was placed on testing and reflecting on how individual tools could support local intervention and policy design. The final part of each session included a collective demonstration highlighting the overarching aims and structure of the Equal-Life Toolbox, illustrating how individual tools fit within the broader exposome approach.

These sessions were specifically tailored to a diverse group of local stakeholders involved in shaping children's environments, including teachers and school directors, municipal officers, architects, urban planners, parents, students, and professionals working in public and mental health. The interactive format allowed for rich discussion, peer learning, and context-specific insights relevant to the implementation of exposome-informed practices.

5.3.1 Ljubljana 11 November 2024

This in-person training session in Ljubljana focused on applying selected tools from the Equal-Life project to real-world cases in the field of spatial and urban planning. The session prioritised hands-on engagement with two key instruments deriving from the Equal-Life project:

- The Equity Assessment Tool
- The Logic Model

Participants worked on practice-based exercises that encouraged critical thinking and discussion around the integration of social and health equity into spatial planning processes. In the final part of the training day, a broader demonstration of the Equal-Life Toolbox was provided, showcasing its overall aims and how the different tools interconnect within the exposome framework.

Training Objectives

The main objectives of the training and stakeholder involvement in Ljubljana were:

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- **Improve consideration of social aspects in spatial/urban planning**

Raise awareness of how equity concerns can be embedded into spatial planning and environmental impact assessment. Promote the use of tools that support equity-sensitive approaches in planning practice.

- **Promote child-centred perspectives across settings**

Emphasise the importance of addressing children's needs across various life settings (e.g. home, neighbourhood, kindergarten, school).

Encourage planning and policy design that takes into account children's developmental stages and their unique vulnerabilities.

- **Promote an equity approach**

The equity model was introduced and used in the interactive sessions.

- **Highlight the role of early-life environmental exposures**

Increase understanding of how early exposure to environmental factors can affect cognitive and mental health development.

- **Enable interdisciplinary collaboration**

Foster the creation of a national and European network of professionals across public health, spatial planning, education, and local governance.

Target Stakeholders

The Ljubljana training was tailored to a diverse group of stakeholders involved in shaping children's physical and social environments, including:

- Teachers and school directors
- Municipal officials and local planners
- Architects and urbanists
- Parents and students
- Public health and mental health professionals

Programme breakdown:

Session 1: Introducing Equal-Life and the Exposome

Aim: To present the Equal-Life project, key findings, and the exposome approach.

Content:

- Introduction to the project and its goals
- Overview of findings on physical, social, and internal exposures

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Presentation on the social dimension of the exposome
- Discussion of relevant indicators and causal links

Session 2: Applying Tools to Local Cases

Aim: To explore how the Equal-Life approach and tools can be applied in practice.

Case Studies Presented by Stakeholders:

- UIRS: Planning green areas for physical activity (PREZENCA project)
- IPOP: “Actively to School” – promoting walking and cycling
- Young Dragons: Needs of young migrants in Ljubljana
- Jožef Stefan Institute: Cycling through quiet green areas (URBANOME project)

Equity Assessment Framework

- Introduction to the equity tool and assessment phases
- Case example from Utrecht (play spaces plan)
- Group discussions on equity in participants' own cases
- Short group presentations with key reflections
- Final wrap-up and conclusions

Green Space Accessibility Tool

- Tool presentation (Achilleas Psyllidis)
- Indicators developed by UIRS (Ina Šuklje-Erjavec)
- Discussion on tool applicability in local contexts
- Reflections on integrating tools into planning practice

Session 3 - Toolbox Demonstration & Future Ambitions

Aim: To present the Equal-Life Toolbox in its entirety and reflect on future use.

Content:

- Live demonstration of the Equal-Life Toolbox
- Plenary discussion on its usability, relevance to stakeholders, and potential for integration into local and regional practice

Detailed Program in [Annex 4 – In person Ljubljana Training Agenda](#)

Number of participants: ~15 Municipality and City Association representatives (note: a different subset from the Vienna participants)

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

5.3.2 In-Person Training & Conference Contribution – Vienna (EUROCITIES Environment Forum 2024)

Context

As part of the dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities of the Equal-Life project, a light-format training and presentation was delivered during the EUROCITIES Environment Forum 2024, held in Vienna from 12 to 14 November under the theme "A European Deal for Climate and Environmental Justice.

Equal-Life contributed through two complementary formats:

- A conference contribution during the Noise Working Group meeting on 12 November, consisting of a 30-minute session combining an introductory presentation and live demonstration of the Equal-Life Toolbox.
- Participation in the working group Green Areas & Biodiversity by one of the Equal-Life representatives, sharing some Equal-Life exposome insights such as the TUDelft research on accessibility of green areas from the Equal-Life project.

Additionally, the promotion flyers for the Equal-Life project and trainings were distributed throughout the plenary areas, for all participants to obtain.

These activities focused on promotion and dissemination of the Equal-Life project work.

Session Content in working group Noise:

- Brief introduction to the Equal-Life project and its focus on the exposome and children's mental health. Demonstration of the Equal-Life Toolbox (screen recording and explanation)
- Plenary discussion: relevance of the exposome approach in spatial and environmental planning
- Invitation to register for further updates and upcoming trainings

Target Audience

The audience consisted of municipal professionals and experts from the EUROCITIES Network, particularly those involved in the Noise Working Group and Green Areas & Biodiversity (GAB) Working Group. These individuals work on public space, green infrastructure, and climate adaptation, with an emphasis on integrating health and equity into planning processes. The broader EUROCITIES network includes over 90 cities and 20 national networks, representing more than 1,000 municipalities across the WHO EURO region.

Objectives

- Raise awareness of the exposome concept and its applicability in urban and environmental planning
- Present the Equal-Life Toolbox in a clear, accessible format
- Engage city representatives in discussion on practical use of the tools in local contexts

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Lay the groundwork for future participation in the Equal-Life training programme or Eurocities Academy sessions
- Disseminate project outputs to a wide European city network through both live interaction and the official forum booklet

Number of participants: 20 representatives from different WHO members and associations

5.3.3 Amsterdam, linked to End-event Equal-Life – 7 April 2025

Context

The in-person training session held in Amsterdam on 7 April 2025 was organised as a focused event with a dual purpose:

- To present and validate the near-final version of the Equal-Life Toolbox and related concepts.
- To prepare for the general event taking place the following day (8 April), by engaging core stakeholders in structured feedback and reflection.

This session targeted a small, selected group of stakeholders, primarily those who had been closely involved in the project and had followed its progress over time. The goal was to obtain qualified feedback on the project's growth, the usability of the toolbox, and its future operationalisation. A few new stakeholders were also present, allowing for a natural exchange of insights between long-standing and newer participants.

Objectives

- Validate the final structure and content of the Equal-Life Toolbox and guidebook
- Discuss the core concepts of the exposome in relation to children's mental health
- Gather feedback on selected tools and texts, and assess usability through applied exercises
- Explore how to disseminate the toolbox and integrate it into a sustainable business or delivery model
- Prepare participants for the discussions and broader stakeholder engagement scheduled for the General Event on 8 April

Session Content

The session combined short presentations, live demonstrations, and interactive feedback activities. Key highlights included:

- Presentation of selected Equal-Life results, particularly those to be further elaborated during the General Event
- Live demonstration of the near-final version of the toolbox, including key features and structure
- Interactive validation using Slido, allowing stakeholders to respond in real time to questions on key exposome and mental health concepts

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Facilitated discussion on the practical relevance of the toolbox and how core concepts (e.g. environmental exposures, mediators, child development stages) are communicated to end users
- Exploration of future use scenarios, including dissemination strategies and contributions to the business model plan (Deliverable in progress)

Reflections and Outcomes

This session marked a key milestone in the final validation phase of the Equal-Life Toolbox. The combination of experienced project stakeholders and selected external participants ensured high-quality feedback grounded in project knowledge while welcoming fresh perspectives.

The interactive format proved effective in confirming the relevance and clarity of core messages, the usability of toolbox content, and the added value of the guidebook in practical contexts. Discussions also contributed directly to the refinement of the toolbox's dissemination strategy and supported alignment with the broader business model development.

Number of participants: 10 representatives from international cities and associations

5.3.4 Barcelona – “Eurocities Academy” – 5-6 May 2025

Context

The Barcelona training was part of the Eurocities Academy initiative and aimed to operationalise the Equal-Life Toolbox within a structured learning environment for urban policymakers and practitioners. This session focused on applying the exposome framework to support mental health and cognitive development in children through improved urban environments.

Equal-Life addresses the complex relationship between environmental, social, and internal exposures and their influence on child development. The training session translated these insights into actionable knowledge for local government professionals engaged in planning, environmental health, mental health, and policy evaluation.

Objectives

- Introduce the exposome concept and the Equal-Life Toolbox to Eurocities members
- Explore how cumulative exposures (e.g. noise, air pollution, lack of green space, socio-economic factors) affect children's health
- Train participants to use the Equal-Life Toolbox and its components, including the Public Intervention Logic Model
- Enable cities to design exposome-informed action plans tailored to local challenges
- Foster peer learning and transdisciplinary dialogue between city representatives

Programme Structure

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

This training followed a three-phase blended format, combining online and in-person learning:

a) Application Phase

- A call for participants was launched among Eurocities members.
- Applications were screened to select professionals working in relevant areas (urban health, child policy, planning).
- Selected participants received pre-training materials and access to the Equal-Life Toolbox.

b) Pre-Training (Online Sessions)

Two interactive online sessions prepared participants for the in-person event:

- Session 1: Onboarding and Local Challenges
 - Introduction to the programme and participant networking
 - Sharing of local issues related to children’s mental health and urban environments
 - Brief overview of the Equal-Life project and expected outcomes
- Session 2: Introduction to the project and to the Toolbox
 - Introduction presentation by the Equal-Life coordinator, Irene van Kamp
 - Guided walkthrough of the Equal-Life Toolbox
 - Exploration of its relevance in city-specific contexts
 - Encouragement to explore the toolbox independently before the in-person training

c) In-Person Training (Barcelona, May 2025)

- Presentation of key project findings and practical implications for cities
- Toolbox demonstration and individual exploration
- Case study analysis using the toolbox
- Development of action plans by city teams, followed by expert and peer feedback
- Plenary discussion and reflection on next steps

Format and Participation

Format: Presentations, case exercises, group discussions, and toolbox navigation (See [Annex 5: Eurocities detailed agenda and roadmap](#))

Number of participants: ~20 Eurocities member representatives (note: a different subset from the Vienna participants)

Location: Barcelona (Eurocities member city)

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

Materials: All training materials were made available through the Eurocities Academy e-learning platform

5.3.5 Cairo -“Eurocities Academy” – 5-6 May

Context

As part of a broader international programme on the interconnection between climate, migration, and health, Equal-Life contributed to the first training module of a three-year initiative organised by the Italian National Institute for Health, Migration and Poverty (INMP). The event was held in Cairo from 11 to 15 May 2025, in collaboration with the Italian Embassy in Cairo, Galala University, and CGIAR, under the scientific coordination of Domenico De Martinis.

The programme welcomed 50 selected participants (from over 180 applicants), including young professionals, staff from Egyptian ministries, members of international organisations, and university affiliates. The initiative aims to co-develop a shared policy paper on the nexus between climate change, migration, and health.

The Equal-Life contribution took place on 11 May and consisted of a 3-hour workshop titled: "Climate, Childhood, and Complexity: Lessons from the Exposome for Mental Health Futures"

The session aimed to introduce the exposome approach through the lens of Equal-Life findings on children’s mental health, with a specific focus on how climate change amplifies certain environmental and social exposures.

Workshop Components:

- Introduction to the exposome framework, contextualized for climate-health debates
- Summary of relevant Equal-Life findings on children’s mental health and development
- Scenario-based group discussions, adapted to the Egyptian context
- Guided walkthrough of the Equal-Life Toolbox (structure, usability, example cases)
- Open dialogue on mediators, outcomes, and cross-sector applications

The content was based on Session 1 of the Equal-Life training, integrating materials presented in Barcelona, and adapted to reflect the regional context and challenges.

Audience and Engagement

The workshop engaged approximately 30 actively participating stakeholders, many of whom were nominated by the Italian Embassy based on their roles in ministries, scientific institutions, and international agencies in Egypt. The participant group was notably diverse, both in terms of professional background and gender.

Participants expressed particular appreciation for:

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- The inclusion of mental health in environmental and climate-related discussions
- The clarity of the conceptual framing (exposome, mediators, outcomes)
- The potential of the Toolbox to support evidence-informed decision-making

Several participants requested follow-up materials and expressed interest in future Equal-Life updates and training opportunities.

Reflections and Outcomes

Although time constraints prevented a full evaluation through Slido, the interactive discussions revealed a high level of interest and engagement. The session highlighted the need for shared vocabulary and frameworks when addressing complex, multifactorial challenges such as climate-driven health risks in childhood.

The Cairo session provided a valuable opportunity to test how Equal-Life materials can be adapted for international audiences and informed future strategies for context-sensitive communication and dissemination.

5.3.6 Stockholm – Local training 10 June 2025

Context

The Stockholm training was part of the final round of Equal-Life dissemination and capacity-building activities. It was hosted at the Karolinska Institute (KI) and aimed to strengthen stakeholder engagement in Sweden by focusing on the practical application of Equal-Life tools, specifically the Logic Model.

Equal-Life trainings are designed to familiarise local and regional stakeholders with the toolbox and its underlying scientific framework. These events also function as co-creation opportunities where feedback from participants contributes to the finalisation and contextualisation of the tools. In Stockholm, this collaborative approach was particularly relevant given the close engagement of Karolinska-affiliated stakeholders throughout the project.

Target Audience

This session was tailored for a small group of core stakeholders affiliated with Karolinska Institute, including professionals and researchers already involved in or closely following the development of Equal-Life. The training also aimed to connect with the next generation of health and policy professionals, including those working at the intersection of environmental science, urban planning, and child health.

Objectives

- Present key results and practical implications of the Equal-Life project
- Explore the development and use of the Logic Model for policy and intervention design
- Demonstrate the Equal-Life Toolbox and encourage interdisciplinary use

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Gather feedback on the usability of the tools from experienced and early-career professionals

Programme Summary

The training was structured into three core parts:

1. Introduction and Key Results
 - a. Presentation of the Equal-Life project's objectives, methodology, and main findings
 - b. Emphasis on the exposome's impact on children's mental health and cognitive development
 - c. Delivery of the results presentation by a representative from Karolinska Institute, leveraging the institutional context and local relevance
2. Focus Session – The Logic Model
 - a. Overview of the logic model: definition, purpose, development within Equal-Life
 - b. Step-by-step walkthrough of its structure and intended applications
 - c. Group-based hands-on exercise: participants applied the logic model to a sample case
 - d. Reflection and discussion on how such a model could support policy development in their own context
3. Toolbox Demonstration and Interactive Exploration
 - a. Presentation of the (near-final) Equal-Life Toolbox through a video and live navigation
 - b. Individual and group exploration of toolbox features
 - c. Plenary discussion: identifying relevant tools, potential use cases, and barriers to implementation
 - d. Peer exchange to foster cross-disciplinary learning and network building

Reflections and Outcomes

The Stockholm session provided a valuable opportunity to validate the Logic Model in a focused academic and policy-driven setting. Participants appreciated the clarity of the model's structure and its potential for supporting local-level intervention planning.

The session helped reinforce the role of the Equal-Life Toolbox as both a knowledge platform and a practical resource for interdisciplinary collaboration.

Number of participants: 8 representatives from Stockholm municipalities and city associations

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

5.3.7 İzmir – Healthy Cities 20 June 2025

Context

The İzmir training was organised as an official side event of the 2025 WHO Healthy Cities Annual Business Meeting and Technical Conference, hosted at the IzQ Innovation Center in partnership with the Healthy Cities National Network of Türkiye. The session was delivered as part of Equal-Life’s final training programme and marked a significant opportunity to engage with both Turkish and European city stakeholders in a regional urban health and planning context.

The training was organised with the support of the Healthy Cities team (Türkiye) and the Municipality of İzmir, and facilitated by the Equal-Life training team. Simultaneous interpretation was provided throughout the session to ensure accessibility for the diverse group of participants.

Audience

The training gathered 15 participants, including:

- representatives from EU cities
- professionals from Türkiye, selected through national and local networks

Participants represented urban planning departments, municipal health offices, ministries, academic institutions, and NGOs. A strong link was established between the training content and the Kordon waterfront redevelopment site, which served as the basis for the case study exercises.

Objectives

- Present Equal-Life findings and introduce the exposome approach for improving children’s mental health
- Connect project results to real-world urban redevelopment challenges (e.g. Kordon waterfront area)
- Facilitate scenario-based group work to apply Equal-Life concepts
- Introduce and test the Equal-Life Toolbox
- Collect user feedback for refinement and dissemination strategies

Programme Summary

The Equal-Life workshop featured several parts:

- Presentation of project results and key messages, with a discussion linking the findings to what participants observed during the site visit.
- Group work, where participants defined a local case in which the exposome approach could be applied. They then selected relevant Equal-Life results for their case and shared their ideas in breakout sessions.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Toolbox demonstration, including a walkthrough of the Equal-Life Toolbox and time for participants to explore its content individually or in teams. This was followed by a discussion on how useful the toolbox could be in their work.
- Wrap-up, with final reflections on what participants learned, what they would share with colleagues, and how this work connects to broader urban health tools like the Place Standard Tool.

The day ended with closing remarks and a social gathering in the evening.

Reflections and Outcomes

The İzmir training successfully combined local relevance with international insight. The Kordon site visit grounded theoretical discussions in a concrete urban development case, while the interactive format supported exchange between experienced policymakers and emerging professionals. Participants appreciated the structure of the session and the clarity of the Equal-Life concept, particularly the emphasis on mental health, often underrepresented in environmental and planning discussions. The toolbox demonstration prompted rich conversations about usability, adaptability, and potential integration into local policy workflows. This session also strengthened ties with the WHO Healthy Cities Network, creating a pathway for future uptake of the Equal-Life toolbox in cities across Türkiye and beyond.

See detailed Program in [Annex 6: In person training Izmir 2025 detailed program](#)

Number of participants: 20 representatives from different cities in the Healthy cities network

6. Annexes

6.1 Annex 1: Pilot Training Agenda – Amsterdam template

Time	Presenter	Activity
09:00 - 09:15		Walk in, coffee
09:15 - 09:30	Kim van Wijk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening – why are we here today • Who is in the room?
09:30 -10:00	Sonja Jeram & Dirk Schreckenber	Session 1 – The Equal-Life project: background, context and overview Presentation of the Equal-Life project, the exposome and re-researching the link to mental health & cognitive development in children.
10:00 -10:35	Kim van Wijk	Let's practice: review what we learned
10:35 -10:50		Short break
10:50 -11:10	Fred Woudenberg	Exercise continued – Pitch your idea!
11:10 -11:30	Kim van Wijk	Feedback on session 1
11:30 -12:30	Anna Sandionigi & Marco Balduini	Session 2 – Demo & browse of the Toolbox (1 hour) An introduction to the toolbox and time to browse individually. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short intro to the toolbox • Exercise – Dive into the toolbox: browse and explore; Feedback & discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of a dummy use case to navigate the toolbox
12:30-12:40	Kim van Wijk	Feedback on session 2
12:40 -14:00		Lunch break & inspiration walk
14:00 -15:20	Fred Woudenberg & others	Session 3 – Schinkelkwartier: an exposome case We will look at the Schinkelkwartier as a real case to which we can apply the Equal-Life concepts. How can the toolbox help inform you on how to apply the concepts from Equal-Life in practice? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to Schinkelkwartier Background, ambition, opportunities and challenges. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applying the exposome and toolbox to Schinkelkwartier Browse, discuss and interact! <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion & reflection: what have we found?
15:20 -15:40		Break & Feedback
15.40- 15.50	Kim van Wijk	Reflection training team: what have we learned today? & plenary feedback
15:50 -16:00	Fred Woudenberg Kim van Wijk	Short closing and link to ambitions in Amsterdam Final thank you

6.2 Annex 2: Online training Agenda template

Time	Activity
09:30-09:35	Entering “room”
09:35-09:45 (10 min)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who are we – short introduction of the E-L team • Opening – why are we here today • Who is in the room? <i>Open SLIDO</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who do we have in the virtual 'room'? ○ Why are you here? What are you hoping to gain / learn? <p>CLOSE Slido</p>
09:45-09:50 (4 min total)	- Showcase animation
09:50-10:30 (45 min)	<p>Session 1 – Background and context</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Equal-Life project: background, context and overview
10:30-10:40	Open mics for questions or responses
10:40-10:45	5 min break
10:45-11:15	<p>Session 2 – Applying to practice/internalizing content</p> <p>Open SLIDO – Hold a discussion with selected stakeholder first</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What does te exposome look like, in this case? • First: Open ended question; name a few that are entered • SECOND Check box/ranking with factors from the environment and select which represent the exposome. • Now, take children and adolescents as your point of departure, does anything change in your perspective on 'the exposome' ? • Open ended question; discuss • Applying the exposome approach and addressing this population group: what practical/policy changes are needed for your work? (draw from your own experience/work) • Open ended question; discuss
11:15-11:25	<p>Session 3 – Toolbox demo & future ambitions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short introduction of the toolbox (orally) - Screencast toolbox, sharing a short presentation of aims, goal and future plans +- 5 min
10 min	Exploring toolbox
	<p>Short closing</p> <p>Link to upcoming in-person meetings</p>

6.3 Annex 3: Slido general format

Slido questions	
[opening online training]	<p>1. Who do we have in the virtual 'room'?</p> <p>Policy maker Health professional Public health service Urban planner Researcher Education Other</p>
	<p>2. Why are you here? What do you hope to learn? (Open ended question)</p>
	[close slido]
[session 1 presentation] Live + present Jenny's presentation Open mics for discussion? TO DECIDE	
Open slido again for session 2	<p>Showcase 2-3 pictures of an environment with some short explanation</p> <p>3. What does te exposome look like, in this case? First: Open ended question AND SECOND Check box à with factors / all indicators from the environment and select which represent the exposome. ➔ Explain: this indicates that the exposome is different for everyone from different backgrounds.</p> <p>4. Now, take children and adolescents as your point of departure, does anything change in your perspective on 'the exposome' ? Open ended question</p> <p>5. Applying the exposome approach and addressing this population group: what practical/policy changes are needed for your work? (draw from your own experience/work) Open ended question</p>
Session 3: Toolbox demo + Italian training: Marco/Anna live voice over of toolbox	
Open slido	<p>○ Did you find this initial experience with the toolbox comfortable and intuitive? (multiple choice: yes, no)</p>

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

	<p>add: I other (please share- invite them to share their opinion)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Would you share the toolbox with a colleague? (multiple choice: yes, no) Invite people to share why? Is 'maybe' also an option? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Which parts of the toolbox are you interested in using? And could be used in your daily work? ○ Do you think anything is missing, or do you have suggestions to improve the content and usability? (open answer with limited number of character) <p>- Would you like to stay updated on the toolbox progress?</p>
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6.4 Annex 4 – In person Ljubljana Training Agenda

Time	Activity
08:45-09:00	Walk in, coffee
09:00-09:15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why are we here today? • Who is in the room?
09:15-10:00	Session 1 – Equal-Life project: presentation by the Equal-Life team Background, overview and results so far
10:00-10:20	Discussion & reflection: the exposome & mental health and cognitive development in children
10:20-11:00	Session 2 – Applying knowledge and tools to practice – case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Equity assessment tool <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of the Equity Assessment tool • Example of application in an existing case • Questions
11:00-11:20	Break
11:20-12:45	<p>Work in groups on cases from Ljubljana, using the equity assessment tool</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Matej Vinko, NIJZ, Intersectoral Approaches in National Mental Health Programme in Slovenia 2. David Kocman, Jožef Stefan Institute, Building Inclusive and Healthier Cities: A Case Study on Cycling and Urban Stressors through an Urban Living Lab Approach 3. Matteo Hočurščak, Municipality of Ljubljana/Mladi zmaji, Young Dragons, Polje neighbourhood and consideration of adolescents in the area 4. <p>Followed by: Plenary presentations, discussion & conclusions</p>
12:45-14:00	Lunch break & inspiration walk
14:00-14:40	Session 2 – continued, 'Children's access to urban greenspaces' <ul style="list-style-type: none"> B. Conceptual Model of factors and accessibility measures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the Equal-Life conceptual model of factors affecting children's access to urban greenspaces.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Indicators for accessibility to green areas developed in Slovenia Discussion and final conclusions (10 min)
14:40-15:10	Session 3 – Toolbox demonstration & future ambitions <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Demonstration of the Equal-Life toolbox Plenary discussion on toolbox and applicability in practice
15:10-15:30	Presentation on database for Environment, Health and Social Indicators in Slovenia https://gis.stat.si/
15:30 -15:40	Short closing, link to ambitions Ljubljana & final thank you

6.5 Annex 5: Eurocities detailed agenda and roadmap

6.5.1 Roadmap

This roadmap template is designed to help participants translate the knowledge acquired throughout the “Mental health for children: science-based policy-making in cities” training into their local context, reinforcing learning through an applied methodology. It aims to serve as a practical tool for participants to develop actionable strategies once they return to their cities.

The document will evolve throughout the training, with different sections completed at specific stages. Sections 1 and 2 must be prepared before the training, as outlined in the programme guide, while Sections 3 and 4 will be developed, peer-reviewed, and finalised during the in-person sessions.

As a working draft, the roadmap does not require formal approval or adoption by city councils but must be submitted to organisers at the end of the training. Its purpose is to facilitate applied learning and support participants in creating a basis for concrete action in their cities.

6.5.1.1 Section 1: initial ideas

Goal:

To prompt participants to reflect on how their city currently analyses children’s needs and formulates policies for mental health and development. This section aims to help participants identify strengths and gaps in their city’s approach before exploring how the exposome framework could enhance policymaking (which will be done later in the training).

Guiding questions:

- *To what extent is children’s mental health currently addressed in the city administration?*
- *Which city departments are involved in policymaking for child development and mental health?*
- *What data or evidence is used to guide decision-making on child policy?*
- *What does this structure suggest about the city’s understanding of child development?*

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6.5.1.2 Section 2: city challenge

Goal:

To identify and present a city challenge that will serve as the basis for the exposome analysis during the in-person training. Participants should select a real-life case from their city that relates to children’s mental health and development, offering an opportunity to explore how policy can be improved.

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

Criteria for selecting the city challenge:

1. *Be directly relevant to children’s mental health: focus on environments where children live, learn, or play, considering both mental wellbeing and cognitive development.*
2. *Have a well-defined geographic scope: ideally focus on a neighbourhood or district, capturing both social and physical factors in a manageable area.*
3. *Highlight the interaction of multiple factors: involve both social (e.g. economic conditions, family structure), and physical (e.g. pollution, urban design) influences.*
4. *Be actionable and connected to policymaking: allow for the identification of concrete interventions and align with ongoing or planned city initiatives.*

Guiding questions to present the challenge:

- a. *Context and relevance:*
 - *What is the specific challenge, and why is it important for children’s mental health?*
 - *Which group of children (age, socioeconomic background...) are most affected?*
 - *In which neighbourhood or district is this issue most evident?*
 - *What are the main social, physical, and governance features of the neighbourhood/district?*
- b. *Current policy landscape:*
 - *What policies or programmes currently address this issue?*
 - *What city departments and stakeholders are currently involved, and which are missing from the conversation?*
 - *What are the main limitations or gaps in the current approach?*
- c. *Alternative approaches:*
 - *How else could this challenge be addressed? What alternative perspectives or approaches could be considered?*

6.5.1.3 Section 3: exposome analysis

Goal of the section:

To apply the exposome analytical framework to the selected city challenge, identifying how different environmental, social, and internal factors interact to influence children’s mental health and development. This section will support participants in using the Equal-Life toolbox to better understand the complexity of exposures and their policy implications.

Key elements to consider:

- **Multi-dimensional approach:** *How is the challenge currently framed – does it mainly consider social or physical aspects only? What additional dimensions (social, physical, biological) could be integrated under an exposome-based analysis? Are there links between environmental exposures (e.g. air pollution, noise),*

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

social conditions (e.g. income disparities, access to services), and biological factors that are not currently considered?

- **Data and evidence:** *What sources of information exist in the city to assess these factors? Are there gaps in the data that could be addressed through an exposome-informed approach?*
- **Policy implications:** *How could a broader exposome-based perspective influence policy interventions? What new insights might emerge from using this approach compared to the city's existing methods?*

More detailed instructions and methodological guidance will be provided as the programme progresses. Participants will receive guidance on how to use the Equal-Life toolbox and apply it to their city challenge during the in-person training.

6.5.1.4 Section 4: from scientific knowledge to policy action

Goal of the section:

To identify policy implications from the exposome analysis, understand barriers to implementing these recommendations, and devise strategies to overcome these barriers.

Policy recommendations

Goal:

To translate the findings from the exposome analysis into specific policy actions aimed at improving children's mental health and development.

Guiding Questions:

- *Based on the exposome analysis, what key actions or decisions could improve children's mental health in your city?*
- *How do these recommendations align with or challenge current city policies?*
- *What precise measures could be implemented to address the identified needs?*
- *What does this involve in terms of governance – which other city departments should be involved and with what role?*

Barriers to implementation

Goal:

To identify potential barriers that could hinder the implementation of selected policy recommendations.

Guiding Questions:

- *What challenges might arise when attempting to implement these actions?*
- *Are there structural or procedural issues within the city administration that could pose obstacles (e.g., lack of interdepartmental collaboration, limited resources)?*

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- *How might external factors such as political priorities, community demands, or industry lobby?*

Strategies to overcome barriers

Goal:

To develop strategies for addressing identified obstacles and ensuring the recommendations can be effectively implemented.

Guiding Questions:

- *What specific steps could you take to gain political or community support for these actions?*
- *How could you foster collaboration between departments or stakeholders to support implementation?*
- *What evidence or communication strategies could be used to convince decision-makers of the value of these policies?*

6.5.2 Agenda

Day 1: understanding urban impacts' on children's mental health through the exposome			
	Session	Description	Trainer(s)
09:00-09:15	Walk-in and registration		
09:15-09:45	Welcome, introduction and agenda of the day		
09:45-11:15	Session 1 – Impacts on child development: understanding the exposome	<p>The goal of this session is to refresh participants about the exposome and its relevance to children's mental health and cognitive development.</p> <p>It will start with an introduction on the overall importance of mental health in urban settings, followed by a revisit of online session 2 (exposome toolbox), and a focus on research outcomes and key takeaways from it.</p> <p>After this presentation, open exchanges among participants and with the experts will be facilitated, to make the connection with participating cities' challenges.</p>	<p>Sonja Jeram (lead), National Institute of Public Health Slovenia (NIJZ)</p> <p>Jordi Júlvez, Pere Virgili Health Research Institute (IISPV) and Barcelona Institute for Global Health (ISGlobal)</p>

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

11:15-11:30	Coffee break	
11:30-13:00	<p>Session 2 – Making the exposome digestible: from exposome to indicators</p>	<p>This session aims to provide participants with different tools and approaches to turn the exposome concept into concrete indicators that cities can use to develop data-driven strategies.</p> <p>For that, the session will start with basic guidelines on how to measure the exposome, followed by a presentation on how different approaches to the exposome (focusing on different exposures) can be differently translated into indicators. This will be developed on the basis of the two set of indicators used by ISGlobal and TU Delft, and will be then followed by a presentation on the applicability of resulting indicators and measurement models in practice. An open discussion with participants will close this section.</p> <p>The session will end with a link to the toolbox, showing how the different tools and approaches discussed can be found in the Equal-Life Toolbox.</p>
13:00-14:00 Lunch and site visit to the greening project around the venue		
14:00-15:30	<p>Session 3 – A real-life case study</p>	<p>This session aims to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application by exploring a real-world example of how urban environments can influence children's mental health through the exposome lens. Participants will examine a concrete case study presented by Mark Nieuwenhuijsen on the city of Barcelona, based on research conducted at ISGlobal, and complemented by insights from the City of Utrecht. The goal is to help participants see how exposome-based approaches can be translated into tangible actions at city level.</p> <p>The session will begin with a presentation of the case study context, challenges identified, data collected, and the exposome-related interventions proposed or implemented. This will be followed by an interactive discussion, where participants will be encouraged to critically analyse the case, draw lessons applicable to their own contexts, and reflect on the added value of using the exposome framework for policy development.</p>
15:30-15:45 Coffee break		

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

15:45-17:00	Session 4 – Applying the toolbox to city challenges	The goal of this session is to translate the knowledge about the exposome acquired so far into participants' local challenges. It will start with a re-introduction of the toolbox built-up, and then participants will work on their own city challenges, with the support and advice from Equal-Life experts.	Anna Sandionigi , Quantia Consulting
17:00-17:30	Wrap-up		
<p>Site visit: Barcelona's Superblock</p> <p>The site visit will take participants to one of Barcelona's emblematic Superblocks (Superilles), a flagship initiative aimed at reclaiming public space for people, reducing motorised traffic, and creating healthier, more liveable urban environments. This visit will allow participants to explore how a multi-faceted urban intervention can improve physical, social, and mental well-being — particularly for children.</p> <p>Guided by training participants from the City of Barcelona, the visit will showcase how the Superblocks integrate elements of environmental sustainability, mobility, public health, and equity, and how these transformations align with the goals of the exposome approach. Participants will have the opportunity to observe on-site features, ask questions, and reflect on how similar interventions could be adapted or replicated in their own cities to promote children's mental health and cognitive development.</p>			

Day 2: translating science into policy			
	Session	Description	Trainer(s)
09:00-09:15	Walk-in		
09:15-09:30	Welcome and agenda of the day		
09:30-10:15	Keynote presentation on Barcelona's mental health policies for children	<p>This keynote session will offer an insider perspective on how the City of Barcelona addresses children's mental health through public policy. Javier Rodríguez, Commissioner for Children, Youth and LGBTI Policies, will present the city's vision, challenges, and strategies in this area.</p> <p>The presentation will explore the main mental health challenges affecting children in Barcelona, the city's current policy responses, and the factors considered in designing these policies. Particular attention will be given to whether and how a multi-dimensional approach — integrating biological, social, economic, environmental and urban factors — shapes the city's interventions. The Commissioner will also discuss how Barcelona monitors progress through, the main barriers to strengthening these policies (such as data gaps or interdepartmental coordination), and key</p>	Javier Rodríguez , Commissioner for Children, Youth and LGBTI policies, City of Barcelona

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

		<p>lessons learned that could inspire other cities. The session will last 45 minutes, combining the presentation with an open discussion segment, allowing participants to ask questions and exchange views with the speaker.</p>	
10:15-11:30	<p>Session 5: Translating scientific knowledge into policy action</p>	<p>This session will focus on the critical step of transforming scientific evidence into effective urban policies that promote children’s mental health. Drawing on examples from Utrecht and a literature review, participants will explore the common challenges encountered when trying to bridge the gap between research and practice,</p> <p>The session will start with short presentations setting the scene, followed by a structured discussion where participants will be invited to reflect on their own cities' contexts. Together, we will identify strategies for making scientific insights actionable in municipal policymaking, and for embedding multi-dimensional approaches like the exposome into concrete plans and interventions. The session will combine presentations, interactive dialogue, and peer exchange to facilitate mutual learning.</p>	<p>Miriam Weber, City of Utrecht</p> <p>Guillem Ramírez Chico, Eurocities</p>
11:30-11:45	Coffee break		
11:45-13:00	<p>Session 6: Peer-review</p>	<p>The final working session of the training is dedicated to peer review and collective reflection. The goal is to create a space where participants can share the preliminary work they have developed using the Equal-Life toolbox, receive feedback from peers and experts, and exchange ideas for further improvement.</p> <p>Participants will be invited to briefly present their initial roadmap drafts, focusing on how they have applied the exposome approach to their identified city challenge and the first policy insights they have drawn. Feedback will be structured around guiding questions designed to encourage constructive, supportive exchanges. This session will also allow participants to consolidate their learning, and take inspiration from the experiences of others, consolidating into it all into a final roadmap they can bring back home.</p>	<p>Achilleas Psyllidis, Delft University of Technology</p> <p>Guillem Ramírez Chico, Eurocities</p>

D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

13:00-13:30	Wrap-up, feedback and closing	<p>The final session of the training will provide a space to collectively reflect on the learning experience and gather feedback to inform future improvements. Participants will be invited to share their impressions through a brief, structured discussion, focusing on the relevance, applicability and organisation of the training.</p> <p>In addition to the open exchange, all participants will be asked to complete a short evaluation questionnaire to systematically collect feedback on both the content and format of the programme. This will help the Equal-Life team refine the training materials and toolbox further, and ensure that future Eurocities Academy initiatives continue to meet the needs of city practitioners. The session will conclude with final remarks from the organisers.</p>	Miriam Weber , City of Utrecht Simon Cutler , Eurocities
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6.6 Annex 6: In person training Izmir 2025 detailed program

Programme

Healthy Cities Annual Business Meeting and Technical Conference, 2025

Izmir Side Event Tentative Program, Friday June 20

08:30 - 09:00 Registration (IzQ Innovation Center)

09:00 - 10:00 Opening Speeches

10:00 - 11:45 Plenary Presentation

Miriam Weber: introduction to Equal-Life project

11:45 - 12:30 Kordon Site Visit

12:30-13:50 Lunch (IzQ Innovation Center)

14:00-16:30 Parallel Workshops

1. Key Messages/results presentation (20 min)

- Discussion and reflection on results and key messages (20 min)
- o Link to Waterfront site visit: what do you recognize from the waterfront, looking at the Equal-Life results?

2. Group work: define a “case” where you could use the exposome approach to mental health (20 min)

- Hand out key results and circle what is of use in this case? (20 min)
- Present use cases in larger subgroups (3 groups together) (20 min)
- Plenary reporting back what stood out in this exercise (10 min)

3. Introduction toolbox (15 min)

- Explore toolbox individually or in teams: find some initial material or inspiration for your defined cases (previous session) (15 min)
- Discussion on use of the toolbox (10min)
- Would a toolbox as such help you? In which way?

43

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D9.6 – Training Protocol and Deployments

- Would you share it with others? Etc.
- 6. **Final wrap up: What do you take away from this session?**
- What would you tell your colleagues?
- What is your hope for this field of research and policy for mental health?
- Place standard tool: where do we find overlap? (EVT)
- Who wants to report back in the plenary?

16:30 - 17:00 Final Words & Closing (IzQ Innovation Center)

17:00 - 19:00 Free Time

19:00 - 21:00 COP İzmir Launch and Cocktail (APIKAM, Ahmet Piriştina City Archive and Museum)

